

Expanding the role of proteoforms in the field of infectious disease

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Proteoforms & infectious disease: two main axes

- Characterization of proteoforms involved in infection (*understanding of the pathogenicity*)

Smith *et al.*, *Science Advances* 7, eabk0734 (2021)

- Proteoform-based discrimination of bacterial pathogens (*diagnosis in hospital settings*)

Neisseria meningitidis

PilE proteoform analysis (reference strain)

Coll. G. Duménil (IP)

Pili modification with PG facilitates systemic invasion and the spread of colonization to close contacts

J. Chamot-Rooke et al., *Science* 331, 778 (2011)
Quagliariello V., *N. Engl. J. Med.*, 364, 16, 1573 (2011)

PiE proteoform analysis (hypervirulent clinical strains)

- Hypervirulent clinical isolates collected from patients with evidence of meningitis
- Selection of several isolates from variable location and serogroup

Coll. M-C. Ploy (Limoges)

Unexpectedly high level of glycosylation associated with immune escape

J. Gault et al. *Proteomics*, 14, 1141 (2014)
J. Gault et al. *PLoS Pathog.* 11 (2015)

Bacterial identification in hospitals (MALDI-TOF)

Proteoform-based discrimination of bacterial pathogens

- Objective: Use top-down proteomics to characterize bacterial pathogens in a clinical context
(Collaboration with 3 French hospitals)

- Differentiation of enterobacterial pathogens (12 strains, 3 replicates)

Optimization of the top-down proteomics workflow

MS parameters (Orbitrap Lumos)

AGC target (ms)	100; 250; 500
charge-state exclusion	yes; no
DDA mode	top N: 2, 4, 6; top speed: 5 s
μ scans (MS) ^a	1; 2; 3; 4; 6; 12; 24
MS resolution	15k; 30k; 60k; 120k
μ scans (MS/MS) ^a	2; 3; 4; 6; 12
MS/MS resolution	30k; 60k; 120k
MS/MS mode	ETD (@5 ms; @10 ms); HCD (@15NCE; @20NCE; @25NCE); EThcD (@10 ms@5NCE; @10 ms@10NCE)

- Optimized conditions
- PBS buffer, C4 nanoLC column
 - 60k MS & MS/MS, 2 μ scans, Top4, EThcD
 - ~ 500 proteoforms (ProsightPD) in a single run

Proteoform-based differentiation

Phylogenetic Tree for *E. coli*, *Shigella*, *Salmonella* (3,500 proteoforms, ProSightPD)

YegP Discriminating Proteoforms

A.

YegP proteoforms		<i>Shigella</i>			<i>Escherichia coli</i>				
Proteoform	Theo. Mass [Da]	<i>sonnei</i>	<i>flexneri 2a</i>	<i>flexneri 3</i>	O157:H7 (Stx 1 & 2)	O157:H7	O26:H11 (Stx 1 & eae)	O26:H11 (eae)	MG1655 (K12)
P1	11885.93								x
P2	11855.92	x		x			x	x	
P3	11828.91				x	x			

B.

P1	$M_{\text{measured}} = 11\ 885.94\ \text{Da}$	N A G W F L E L S K L S S D N Q F R F V L K A G N G E L T	25
	$M_{\text{theoretical}} = 11\ 885.93\ \text{Da}$	26 I L T S E L Y T S K A L S A E K G I A S V R S N S P	50
	$\Delta\text{mass} = 0.003\ \text{Da}$	51 Q L E L R Y L E K K T A S N G K F Y F N L K A A N H Q	75
	$-\log\ \text{P-score} = 137.2$	76 I I G S S Q M Y A T A Q L S R E T G I A S V K A N G	100
	% residue cleavage = 58	101 T S L Q T V K D N T C	
Matching fragments = 92			
P2	$M_{\text{measured}} = 11\ 855.91\ \text{Da}$	N A G W F L E L S K L S S D N Q F R F V L K A G N G E L T	25
	$M_{\text{theoretical}} = 11\ 855.92\ \text{Da}$	26 I L T S E L Y T S K A L S A E K G I A S V R S N S P	50
	$\Delta\text{mass} = -0.010\ \text{Da}$	51 Q L E L R Y L E K K T A S N G K F Y F N L K A A N H Q	75
	$-\log\ \text{P-score} = 132.5$	76 I I G S S Q M Y A T A Q L S R E T G I A S V K A N G	100
	% residue cleavage = 62	101 T S L Q L T V K D N T C	
Matching fragments = 99			
P3	$M_{\text{measured}} = 11\ 828.99\ \text{Da}$	N A G W F L E L S K L S S D S Q F R F V L K A G N G E L T	25
	$M_{\text{theoretical}} = 11\ 885.91\ \text{Da}$	26 I L T S E L Y T S K A L S A E K G I A S V R S N S P	50
	$\Delta\text{mass} = 0.076\ \text{Da}$	51 Q L E L R Y L E K K T A S N G K F Y F N L K A A N H Q	75
	$-\log\ \text{P-score} = 135.1$	76 I I G S S Q M Y A T A Q L S R E T G I A S V K A N G	100
	% residue cleavage = 59	101 T S L Q T V K D N T C	
Matching fragments = 93			

DiagnoTop: a new computational pipeline

- Compares TDP datasets and extract discriminative MS/MS spectra without database search

Coll. P. Carvalho

Results for the 12 enterobacterial strains

Strains	DiagnoTop		ProsightPD	
	Total clusters	Exclusive clusters	Total proteoforms	Exclusive proteoforms
<i>Salmonella</i> Enteritidis	1750	1156	1190	521
<i>Salmonella</i> Typhimurium	1732	1716	863	375
<i>Salmonella</i> Newport	1342	654	578	139
<i>Salmonella</i> Muenchen	1222	706	473	147
<i>Shigella</i> sonnei	1319	560	432	84
<i>Shigella</i> flexneri 2a	1248	759	532	189
<i>Shigella</i> flexneri 3	1277	618	430	77
<i>E. coli</i> O157H7 (Stx 1 & 2)	1335	537	454	58
<i>E. coli</i> O157H7	1366	475	604	105
<i>E. coli</i> O26:H11 (Stx 1 & eae)	1443	659	499	97
<i>E. coli</i> O26:H11 (eae)	1617	782	644	175
<i>E. coli</i> K12	1220	333	478	82

Higher number of discriminative features with DiagnoTop

Reduced computing time for DiagnoTop (6h30 vs 10 days)

Data visualization

Discrimination of enterobacterial pathogens without database search

Most recent developments: DiagnoMass

P. Carvalho, M. Santos

Phylogenetic tree built
in 12 minutes!

Future direction

Improved Instrumentation (higher mass)

**Orbitrap Tribrid Eclipse: PTCR
(2021)**

Modification of a Q-
Exactive to install an
Omnitrap

Improved Data Analysis

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